

IMPROVEMENT OF THE SPINDLE DESIGN FOR HORIZONTAL SPINDLE COTTON HARVESTERS

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Abstract. This article is dedicated to the main technical issues encountered in the spindle of horizontal spindle cotton harvesters and solutions to address them. Additionally, it outlines ways to simplify maintenance and reduce costs through a new design that allows easy replacement of the spindle's wearable teeth.

Keywords: cotton harvester, harvesting apparatus, horizontal conical-toothed spindle, vertical cylindrical-toothed spindle.

Mechanization of Cotton Harvesting is currently one of the most important issues in agriculture. Numerous studies have been conducted to automate the cotton harvesting process and develop this technology. Although vertical spindle cotton harvesters developed in 1937-38 were the first major steps in this field, they did not provide sufficient effectiveness. While technology has significantly advanced to date, challenges remain.

One of the key technological advancements is the development of horizontal spindle cotton harvesters. Notably, horizontal spindle machines of the KEYS-2022 model and, subsequently, TIST CE-220 machines developed in collaboration with Uzbekistan are widely used. However, these machines are not always compatible with our cotton varieties. According to scientists, these machines have several drawbacks, including the complexity of maintenance and repair, high cost, and the need for special conditions to achieve high efficiency in the cotton harvesting process.

From the history of spindles, it is known that the primary drawback of both vertical and horizontal spindles is the complexity and labor intensity of repairs when their teeth wear out or if one suddenly breaks under field conditions. Specifically, to repair the spindles of the TIST CE-220 cotton harvester, 864 conical-toothed integral spindle units must be removed, loaded onto a transport vehicle, taken to a repair workshop, unloaded, repaired, reloaded, returned to the farm, unloaded again, and installed in the harvesting apparatus. The only way to eliminate this problem is to create a modular spindle design where the teeth can be replaced in place without removing the spindles, as previously recommended for non-repairable teeth.

To positively address this issue, a new spindle design was developed that allows the replacement of worn teeth by simply removing a single screw, enabling the teeth to last for two or even three seasons without repair.

The proposed spindle scheme

The Horizontal Spindle 1 is fitted with a concave profile roller 2 (viewed from the tip of the tooth) to match the circular construction of the wedge-belt clamp, a hollow shaft 3, and three Z-shaped replaceable toothed bars 4, each positioned in longitudinal slots at a 120° angle to one

another. The bars are designed with opposing outer 5 and inner 6 teeth on their profile. To hold bar 4 in place, a separator 7 is pressed into the inner diameter of shaft 3 with a threaded hole 8, into which a support screw 10 is tightened to limit the longitudinal movement of bar 4.

Usage of the Proposed Replaceable-Tooth Cylindrical Spindle: When working in the field, if a spindle tooth encounters an obstacle and unexpectedly breaks or becomes unusable due to wear (for example, at the end of the season), there is no need for special repair operations, such as removing it from the drum, as is required with the TIST CE-220 machine spindles. Instead, the conical limiting support 9 is removed by loosening the screw 10 in the threaded hole 8, and the worn outer tooth 5 is rotated out from the hollow shaft 3 by 180° to bring the unworn inner tooth 6 into working position. After that, the limiting support 9 is replaced and tightened back with screw 10. With only a screwdriver, all repairs can be performed. Using improved spindles with this design eliminates all the previously mentioned labor-intensive operations, excessive costs, and time losses.

It can be recognized that the only solution to overcome these shortcomings is to replace horizontal and vertical spindles with a completely new inclined spindle cotton picking machine (apparatus). This approach could establish a new direction in the history of cotton-picking apparatuses by introducing inclined spindle cotton harvesters.

To address these issues, we propose new ideas and solutions. Among them, improvements are being made to the design of cotton-picking apparatuses with inclined spindles and conical drums. This apparatus would simplify maintenance and enhance the efficiency of cotton picking.

With the advanced design of cylindrical-shafted spindles featuring replaceable teeth, machine efficiency can be increased. Instead of disassembling and repairing spindles, simply replacing the teeth will ease the maintenance process, reducing costs and saving time. Additionally, the new cotton-picking apparatus designs will overcome the shortcomings of both horizontal and vertical spindles.

Conclusion

Thus, improving cotton harvesting machines remains a pressing issue in a technology. Through new designs and proposed innovative solutions, there is an opportunity to enhance the quality of the cotton harvesting process, simplify maintenance, and introduce significant advancements in agricultural mechanization. This will make a substantial contribution to increasing the efficiency of cotton harvesters.

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